

Isothiocyanatochromates of Tetrakis (1,10-phenanthroline)Cerium(IV)[†]

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COMPOUNDS of the type $[M(L)_n]_3[Cr(NCS)_6]_4$, where $M = Ce^{IV}$, Th^{IV} or U^{IV} ; $L =$ aminopyrine, antipyrine, pyridine or dimethylformamide, and $n = 6$ or 8 have been synthesised and studied¹. We describe here preparation and characterisation of a series of compounds of the type $[Ce(phen)_4][Cr(NCS)_6(L)_3]_4$ and $[Ce(phen)_4][Cr(NCS)_6(L')_3]_4$, where $L =$ ammonia, aniline, *o*-toluidine, *p*-toluidine, urea or thiourea, and $L' =$ phen or bipy (phen = 1, 10-phenanthroline and bipy = 2,2'-bipyridine). The nature of bonding in the parent isothiocyanatochromate anions is unaffected due to the presence of cationic complex moiety.

Experimental

The $[Ce(phen)_4](NO_3)_4$ was prepared as follows: $(NH_4)_2[Ce(NO_3)_6]$ (1.1 g) in acetone (10 ml) was mixed with a solution of triphenylphosphine-oxide (1.1 g) in acetone (10 ml). To the filtrate, phen (1.1 g) (dried at 70°) dissolved in acetone (15 ml) was added². The complex was washed with acetone and dried *in vacuo*.

The chromium complexes were prepared by methods reported earlier³⁻⁶. $NH_4[Cr(NCS)_6]$ (NH_3)₂ (B.D.H., England) was used as such.

Preparation of complexes: To a 1 : 1 aqueous methanolic suspension of $[Ce(phen)_4](NO_3)_4$ was added a solution of respective isothiocyanatochromate in methanol in stoichiometric quantities. The

contents were stirred for 2 h to precipitate out pink coloured compounds which were collected on a buchner funnel and then washed with water and dried.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses, significant ir absorption frequencies and magnetic moment (per Cr^{III} ion) of the compounds are summarised in the Table 1. The evidence for the coordination of phen can be inferred by the position of C=C, C=N, ring stretching, C-H in-plane, ring breathing and C-H out-of-plane vibrations. These bands lie at ~1600, ~1540, ~1470, ~1380, ~1273, ~995 and ~845 cm^{-1} , respectively in the spectra of complexes indicating coordination⁷.

The ir studies have previously been useful in elucidating the nature of bonding in metal thiocyanate complexes^{8,9}. The absorption frequencies due to C-N, C-S stretching and N-C-S bending in all the isolated compounds in the 2040-2100, 780-860 and ~480 cm^{-1} range, respectively are characteristic of N-bonding¹⁰, which indicates that cerium complex moiety does not affect the nature of bonding in the parent isothiocyanatochromates^{11,12}.

Significant negative shift in asymmetric and symmetric N-H stretchings in the spectra of amine, aniline and toluidine complexes indicate the presence of coordinated bases. Similarly, a remarkable shift of the C=O and C=S stretchings in the spectra of the urea and thiourea complexes confirm the presence of the base inside the coordination sphere^{13,14}. In case of phen and bipy complexes diagnostic bands have coupled with similar vibrations of the cationic moiety⁷. Conductance measurement in dimethylformamide clearly indicates that the compounds are ~1 : 4 electrolyte. The magnetic moments per Cr^{III} ion are found to be in range 3.70 to 4.0 B.M. at room temperature.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC MOMENT AND SIGNIFICANT INFRARED DATA (cm^{-1}) OF ISOLATED COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} (R.T.) B.M.	NCS vibration		
			Cl	NCS	O	H		ν_{ON}	ν_{CS}	δ_{NCS}
1.	$[Ce(phen)_4][Cr(NCS)_6(ammonia)_3]_4$	Pink	6.34 (6.57)	41.80 (43.54)	36.68 (36.02)	2.50 (2.62)	3.87	2100 vs	822 w	475 m
2.	$[Ce(phen)_4][Cr(NCS)_6(aniline)_3]_4$	Light violet	4.98 (5.11)	31.95 (33.88)	48.72 (49.05)	3.08 (3.20)	4.06	2090 vs	805 w	480 m
3.	$[Ce(phen)_4][Cr(NCS)_6(o\text{-toluidine})_3]_4$	Rose	5.24 (4.91)	31.14 (32.55)	50.90 (50.49)	3.12 (3.64)	3.78	2080 vs	820 w	480 m
4.	$[Ce(phen)_4][Cr(NCS)_6(p\text{-toluidine})_3]_4$	Rose	4.80 (4.91)	32.35 (32.55)	51.24 (50.49)	3.54 (3.64)	—	2080 s	820 w	—
5.	$[Ce(phen)_4][Cr(NCS)_6(urea)_3]_4$	Light violet	5.94 (5.66)	36.74 (37.50)	35.02 (34.90)	2.38 (2.58)	3.88	2100 brs	800 w	480 w
6.	$[Ce(phen)_4][Cr(NCS)_6(thiourea)_3]_4$	Light violet	5.46 (5.38)	34.82 (35.65)	33.16 (33.18)	2.68 (2.45)	3.68	2090 s	815 w	—
7.	$[Ce(phen)_4][Cr(NCS)_6(phen)_3]_4$	Light pink	5.30 (5.34)	35.10 (35.43)	47.20 (47.63)	2.20 (2.44)	3.77	2095 s	822 w	475 m
8.	$[Ce(phen)_4][Cr(NCS)_6(bipy)_3]_4$	Light pink	5.24 (5.16)	33.82 (34.18)	49.20 (49.48)	2.24 (2.35)	3.83	2095 s	815	475 m

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Synthesis and Infrared Studies of Dioxouranium(VI) Chelates of 2-Ethoxycarbonyl-aminopyridine *N*-Oxide†

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THE coordination chemistry of various oxocations is of interest because of the existence of a strong multiple metal-oxygen covalent bond persisting in various chemical environments. This can be employed as an internal molecular probe to understand more about the nature of metal-ligand bonds in the complexes of these ions¹. Cattalini *et al.*² have summarised various uranyl chelate complexes in a review article. But less is known about the uranyl chelates of aromatic amine *N*-oxides³. In the present communication we wish to report the chelates of uranyl(VI) with 2-ethoxycarbonylamino-pyridine *N*-oxide (ECAPO). The ligand ECAPO has three potential donor sites in tertiary amine *N*-oxygen, imino nitrogen and carbonyl oxygen. Zirconyl(IV) and thorium(IV) chelates of this ligand have already been reported^{4,5}.

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Experimental

Uranyl halides were prepared from nitrate while perchlorate was prepared as reported earlier⁶. The ligand ECAPO was prepared from 2-aminopyridine as reported earlier⁷.

The metal chelates were prepared by mixing the corresponding uranyl(VI) salt in methanol and 2,2'-dimethoxypropane (a dehydrating agent) and the ligand in anhydrous diethyl ether. The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h. In each case the solid product obtained was filtered and washed with methanol and ether. All the chelates were dried *in vacuo* over P₂O₁₀.

All the physical measurements and analyses were performed as reported earlier⁶. Uranium was estimated as U₃O₈. The analytical data are presented in Table I.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data correspond to the compositions UO₂X₂.2ECAPO (X=Cl, Br, or NCS); UO₂(NO₃)₂.ECAPO and UO₂X₂.3ECAPO (X=ClO₄ or I). The molar conductance values of the chelates (in PhNO₂) indicate that chloro, bromo, thiocyanato and nitrate chelates are non-electrolytes, while the iodo and perchlorate chelates dissociate in PhNO₂ and behave as 1 : 2 electrolytes. Hence, in these cases all the anions are present outside the coordination sphere. The molecular weight determination also behaves in the similar way. The magnetic moments of the chelates indicate them to be diamagnetic.

Infrared study: The chelates are characterised on the basis of their ir spectra in 4000-200 cm⁻¹ region. Katritzky and Hands⁹ have examined the ir spectra of heterocyclic ring vibrations of large number of 2-substituted pyridine *N*-oxides. Partial use of their assignments as well as the reports of others¹⁰⁻¹² is made for the assignment of ir bands of ligand and in its metal chelates.

The four main absorption frequencies in ECAPO, namely urethane stretching, N-O stretching, N-O bending and C-H out-of-plane bending deformation are expected to be influenced on chelate formation.

In urethane stretching (R-NH-COOC₂H₅) the carbonyl absorption, responsible for the amide I band, is likely to be lowered. The amide I band in ECAPO appearing at 1730 cm⁻¹ is shifted to lower wave number after forming chelates, indicating a decrease in the stretching force constant of C=O as a consequence of coordination through the carbonyl oxygen atom of the free base. The NH stretching absorption in free ligand occurs at 3200 and 3120 cm⁻¹, which remains unaffected after complexation. This precludes the possibility of coordination through imine nitrogen atom.